

The State Of Small Business And Entrepreneurship In The Economy Of Uzbekistan: Statistical Analysis

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Annotation: This article analyzes the state of small business and entrepreneurship in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2023–2025 based on statistical data. The study focuses on indicators such as the number of small businesses, their share in GDP, their role in the volume of industry and services, as well as their export and territorial distribution. The results of the analysis show that small business plays an important role in economic diversification, increasing employment and export potential, but there are uneven development and structural shortcomings across regions and sectors.

Keywords: small business, entrepreneurship, economic diversification, GDP, microfirms, export, Uzbekistan's economy, statistical analysis

Introduction.

Small business and private entrepreneurship are the main drivers of the economy of any developing country. It provides employment, increases competition in the domestic market, diversifies the types of services and goods, and contributes to economic stability. Based on data published by the National Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan (NSCU), in recent years, the number of small business and entrepreneurship entities in the economy of Uzbekistan, their share in GDP, their role in the volume of industry and services, and their participation in international trade have undergone significant changes. The purpose of this article is to analyze the state of small business, identify trends and key problems based on statistical data.

Methodology.

As the main source of information, data and press releases on “Small Business and Entrepreneurship” on the official website of the Statistics Agency were studied.

Statistical reports, magazines, and media materials published in recent years

(2023–2025) were analyzed.

Through numbers, indicators such as the number of small business entities, their distribution by market sectors, share in GDP, value added by sectors, and participation in exports/imports were extracted.

Results.

The results of the analysis reveal the following key indicators and trends:

Number and dynamics of business entities

At the end of 2023, the number of active small businesses and microfirms amounted to ~ 417.1 thousand.

In 2024, the number of these types of enterprises increased significantly, reaching ~ 561.1 thousand.

As of the beginning of 2025, the number of small business entities increased again, and the total number amounted to ~ 1.21 million - this includes microfirms, small enterprises, individual entrepreneurs, peasant and farmer households.

Small business density (ratio to population): ~ 32.1 small businesses per 1,000 people.

Economic potential and share in GDP

At the end of 2023, the share of small businesses in GDP was 51.2%.

As of June 1, 2024 (6 months from the beginning of the year), the value added created by small businesses was 47.5% of the total gross value added.

Share in value added by sectors: the share of small businesses is significant in sectors such as agriculture, industry, construction, and services. For example, the share of small businesses is high in the agriculture and services segments.

Share in industry, services, and exports

According to 2025 data, small businesses accounted for 33.4% of the total output in the manufacturing industry.

Small businesses also play a key role in agriculture, services, and trade: products and services are created through peasant farms, microfirms, and individual entrepreneurs.

There is also a participation of small business entities in exports and imports: products exported by small businesses account for a significant share of the total export volume.

Territorial distribution and distribution by sector

The geographical location and density of small business entities varies by district and region - there are more entities in cities and densely populated areas, especially in the capital and regional centers.

Entrepreneurship is developing more on the basis of trade, services, and sectors - which indicates flexibility in the needs and demands of the population.

Discussion.

As can be seen from statistical data, small and micro business entities occupy a key place in the economy of Uzbekistan - they have a significant contribution to GDP, industry, services, and exports. These changes are the result of a favorable environment, reforms, subsidies, and simplified procedures created by the state.

At the same time, growth rates and expansion are unevenly distributed across regions and sectors. For example, while there are many micro and small enterprises in the agriculture, trade and services segments, the share of small businesses is lower in the industry and high-tech sectors. This is evidence of problems in diversification and investment targeting.

In addition, despite the high density and share of small businesses in the country, structural problems still exist - staff qualifications, the level of technological modernization, difficulties in meeting the requirements of the domestic and foreign markets. This situation may hinder the long-term sustainable growth of small businesses.

Therefore, additional measures by the state are important - expanding credit and investment opportunities, modernizing infrastructure, training qualified personnel and further strengthening the policy of diversifying markets.

Conclusion. Statistical data show that Uzbekistan is diversifying its economy through small businesses and entrepreneurship, and significant growth is observed

in this sector. Small businesses contribute significantly to GDP, industry, services, and exports. However, there are also uneven developments across sectors and regions, as well as structural weaknesses. If the state and private sectors work together strategically — investing, training, developing market infrastructure, and supporting systems — small businesses can become a stronger foundation for Uzbekistan's economy.

References:

1. Statistics Committee (NSCU). Small Business and Entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, 2023–2025. stat.uz
2. Reports of the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024–2025.
3. World Bank. Doing Business in Uzbekistan, 2023.
4. Sheripov K., Egamov B. O'zbekiston iqtisodiyoti va kichik biznes tahlili, Ma'mun universiteti, 2024.
5. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). Entrepreneurship and SME Development, 2022.
6. Sharipova, Z. (2024). O'zbekistonda tarmoqlararo klasterlarni tashkil etishda davlat siyosatining asosiy yo'nalishlari. Yangi o'zbekistonda tabiiy va ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi.
7. Sharipova, Z. (2024). Tarmoqlararo klasterlar samaradorligini baholash uslubiyati. "XXI asrda innovatsion texnologiyalar, fan va ta'lim taraqqiyotidagi dolzarb muammolar" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(10), 20–24.